

ORGANIZATION OF ALEXANDER FEINBERG'S WORK IN UZBEK LITERATURE

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Annotation: Scientific research on the works of Alexander Arkadyevich Feinberg, the revival of Alexander Feinberg's works in the translation of Uzbek writers, and the skillful translation of masterpieces of Uzbek classic literature into Russian by Alexander Feinberg. Re-studying Feinberg's work and promoting it among young artists.

Key words: Russian language poet, «Chighir» poetry collection, «Yoshlik», «Yangi Dunyo», «Yangi volga», «Ozdamikar» magazines.

Aleksandr Arkadyevich Feinberg is considered to be a writer who made a significant contribution to Uzbek literature in addition to being a Russian poet. It is no exaggeration to say that Feinberg is one of the stars who left a bright and indelible mark on Uzbek literature. Adib was born on November 2, 1939 in Tashkent. He is the author of five poetry collections, four full-length feature film scripts, and more than twenty animated cartoons, whose creative works cannot be repeated in the works of any Uzbek artist. It should be noted that the two-volume book published after the poet's death also testifies to the high attention paid to the writer's work.

Rustam Musurman, who referred to Feinberg's work the most, expressed the following warm and sincere thoughts about the writer.

«Ten years ago, I translated the poems of the People's Poet of Uzbekistan, Alexander Feinberg, according to an editorial assignment. Since the next day was the day of the newspaper, I had to translate five poems from the book «Priisk» from Russian to Uzbek in one night. It was November. I draw and erase what I wrote on paper in the old courtyard, I try to cook the words... That's how my first translation was published in the newspaper «Literature of Uzbekistan»... The poet's poetry fascinated me then. At the same time, I began to translate Alexander Feinberg, not necessarily, but voluntarily. From the thoughts of Rustam Musurman, it can be understood that Feinberg's works can still be a source of creativity for many creative translators. It was Rustam Musurman who translated Feinberg's poems and reached the hands of Uzbek readers in the form of a poetry collection called «Chiğir». Feinberg was a poet who contributed not only to Uzbek literature, but also to Russian and world

literature. Poems of the writer were published in the magazines «Youth», «Change», «Yangi Dunyo», «Yangi Volga», and on a global scale, his works are presented in books in periodicals of countries such as the USA, Canada, and Israel.

The great writer was recognized as the «People's Poet of Uzbekistan» on August 23, 2004 as the first writer of Russian nationality for his great contribution to the literature of independent Uzbekistan.

On August 25, 1999, Alexander Feinberg was awarded the title of «Honored Cultural Worker of the Republic of Uzbekistan» for his achievements and high potential in appreciating the national and spiritual values of Uzbekistan.

On December 3, 2008, he was awarded the «Pushkin» medal by the Russian Federation for his effective work and good works in Russian and Uzbek literature and cultural relations.

The establishment of the Alexander Feinberg scholarship and badge at the Uzbekistan State University of World Languages for the purpose of studying the life and work of Alexander Feinberg, elucidating his activities, and conducting research in the field of scientific research and dissemination is also a sign of the high appreciation of Feinberg's work by our government.

Conclusion: In conclusion, it should be emphasized; Feinberg's creativity is a rich source of creativity not only for today's youth, but also for future generations. I believe that young artists still refer to his creative works.

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